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TO STUDY THE FACTORS THAT IS ENCOURAGING THE CHILD LABOUR IN BARAMULLA DISTRICT OF J&K

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Abstract

Research into the topic of child labour has experienced a significant upswing in the past two decades. Yet despite this increased attention, child labour remains a significant problem in many parts of the world. According to recent estimates by the International Labor Organization (ILO), there were approximately 176 million children between the ages of 5 and 14 in employment in 2008, of which roughly 53 million were participating in hazardous work (Diallo et al., 2010). A common perception is that most child labourers work for wages in the formal sector, conjuring images of children working long hours in sweatshops or toiling away in mines. As a result, consumer boycotts and trade sanctions against products using child labour as an input are often discussed as means of reducing the incidence of child labour. In reality, however, such methods may have little impact for several reasons. Firstly, the majority of working children are active in the agricultural sector, rather than manufacturing (ILO, 2006; Diallo et al., 2010). Secondly, very few children work for wages outside the home; rather, most children are employed by their parents on the family farm or enterprise (Edmonds and Pavcnik, 2005a).

Keywords: Child Labour; International Labor Organization (ILO); Children Working.

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1. Introduction

Child labour is a serious issue of global concern and the problem of child labour is not a concomitant feature of modern society only. In fact, the problem exists since the very dawn of human civilization. The reasons responsible for this phenomenon are varied and have been changing over years. Avenues of child labour over the years have broadened. As a matter of fact, the problem is vexed and wide spread and is not a characteristic of any particular type of economy. Any work, whether manual or mental, which is undertaken by a child, who is below 14 years of age, for monetary consideration, is called child labour. Of these 120 million are

estimated to be in full-time work. Since ages, the prevalence of child labour phenomenon is common in India.

Child labour has presented an explicit challenge to society at least since the industrial revolution. With the progressive adoption of universal primary and secondary education, child labour came into direct conflict with children's access to education, and in many countries the labour of children was withdrawn from production. With the dramatic economic gains of the 20th century child labour became far less prevalent, though the absolute numbers are high. Now the financial and legal means are at hand to address the problem directly, even in the low-income and least developed countries.

Child labour in India is the practice where children engage in economic activity, on part-time or full-time basis. The practice deprives children of their childhood, and is harmful to their physical and mental development. Poverty, lack of good schools and the growth of informal economy are considered as the most important causes of child labour in India.

International Labour Organization (ILO) states that child labour may be defined in a number of different ways, and a different definition yields a different estimate of child labour in India as well as other countries. According to ILO, children or adolescents who participate in work that does not affect their health and personal development or interfere with their schooling, is not child labour; rather it may generally be regarded as being something positive. Such harmless work includes activities such as helping their parents around the home, assisting family or earning pocket money outside school hours and over holidays. These kinds of activities, suggests ILO, may contribute to children's development by providing them with skills and experience, and help to prepare them to be productive members of society during their adult life.

The term child labour, suggested by the International Labour Organization (ILO), is best defined as work that deprives children of their childhood, their potential and their dignity, and that is harmful to physical and mental development. It refers to work that is mentally, physically, socially or morally dangerous and harmful to children, or work whose schedule interferes with their ability to attend regular school, or work that affects in any manner their ability to focus during school or experience healthy childhood.

1.1. International Legal Framework

ILO standards up to 1973

The protection of children from work and at work has been a basic aim of the International Labour Organization since its inception (ILO, 1981, paras. 11 et seq.). Acting on the call for such protection in the Preamble to its Constitution, the ILO adopted the Minimum Age (Industry) Convention, 1919 (No. 5), at the very first session of the International Labour Conference in 1919. Since then the Organization has adopted a further ten Conventions and five Recommendations setting standards on the minimum age of admission to employment or work in industry, agriculture, shipping and other non-industrial occupations. In addition, minimum age standards are also specified in several other Conventions concerned with safety, health and/or general conditions in particular industries.

United Nations International Children's Emergency Fund (UNICEF) defines child labour differently. A child, suggests UNICEF, is involved in child labour activities if between 5 to 11 years of age, he or she did at least one hour of economic activity or at least 28 hours of domestic work in a week, and in case of children between 12 to 14 years of age, he or she did at least 14 hours of economic activity or at least 42 hours of economic activity and domestic work per week. UNICEF in another report suggests, "Children's work needs to be seen as happening along a continuum, with destructive or exploitative work at one end and beneficial work - promoting or enhancing children's development without interfering with their schooling, recreation and rest - at the other. And between these two poles are vast areas of work that need not negatively affect a child's development."

India's Census 2001 office defines child labor as participation of a child less than 17 years of age in any economically productive activity with or without compensation, wages or profit. Such participation could be physical or mental or both. This work includes part-time help or unpaid work on the farm, family enterprise or in any other economic activity such as cultivation and milk production for sale or domestic consumption. The Indian government classifies child labourers into two groups: Main workers are those who work 6 months or more per year. And marginal child workers are those who work at any time during the year but less than 6 months in a year.

Some child rights activists argue that child labour must include every child who is not in school because he or she is a hidden child worker. UNICEF, however, points out that India faces major shortages of schools, classrooms and teachers particularly in rural areas where 90 percent of child labour problem is observed. About 1 in 5 primary schools have just one teacher to teach students across all grades.

The problem of child labour exploitation is a major challenge to the developing countries. Children work at the cost of their right of education which leaves them permanently trapped in the poverty cycle, sadly without the education and literacy required for better paying jobs. Every nation considers the child as a backbone of nation, nation builder and so on, but these words look good only in books.

Child labour is a social stigma on our society. This is particularly serious in India as it tops the list with the highest number of child laborers in the world after Africa. The 2001 census of India estimated the total number of child labour, aged 5-14, to be at 12.06 million. Out of the 12.06 million, 0.12 million engage in hazardous jobs. Child labour is estimated to be a large as 60 million in India as many children are Hidden Workers working in homes or in the underground economy, and that is such economy which makes them handicapped forever. Children are working in the Dhabbas, industries, hotels, and illegally in construction works.

Child labour no doubt, in the long run, evolves into a social and an economic problem as economic disparities widen between poor and educational backward states and that of the faster-growing states. India perhaps has the highest number of laborers in the world that are under 14 years of age. There are several causes behind why the parents of children let their children to work outside the home or let them to live away from their homes. Reasons are often poverty, family subsistence and inadequate public education standard.

Although the constitution of India guarantees free and compulsory education between the ages of 6 to 14, child labour is prevalent in almost in all informal sectors of economy. Many Indian families send their children to work, with some living away from their homes. The worst form of child labor would probably be Bounded Labour. It refers to children who are sold by their parents for money, or to pay off debts and even for a loan.

The problem of child labour continues to pose a big challenge before the country. Government has taken various pro-active measures to tackle this problem. Child labour issue is a Human Rights issue for the whole world. It is a social stigma that should be eradicated.

Childhood is the most innocent phase in human life. It is that stage of life when the human foundations are laid for a successful adult life. Many children, instead of spending it in a carefree and fun-loving manner while learning and playing, are scarred and tormented. They hate their childhood and would do anything to get out of the dungeons of being children and controlled and tortured by others. They would love to break-free from this world, but continue to be where they are, not out of choice, but force. This is the true story of child labor.

Innocent children are employed by industries and individuals who put them to work under grueling circumstances. They are made to work for long hours in dangerous factory units and sometimes made to carry load even heavier than their own body weight. Then there are individual households that hire children as domestic help and beat and physically torture them when they make a mistake. The children are at times made to starve and are given worn out clothes to wear. Such is the story of millions of children in India painful and yet true.

The two primary reasons for the ever-growing social malice of child labor are poverty and lack of education. Poor parents give birth to children thinking them as money-making machines. They carry infants to earn more on the streets from begging. Then as they grow they make them beggars, and eventually sell them to employers. This malady is rampant across the length and breadth of India.

In other words, child labor is any kind of work children are made to do that harms or exploits them physically, mentally, morally, or by preventing access to education. However, all work is not bad or exploitive for children. In fact, certain jobs help in enhancing the overall personality of the child. For example, children delivering newspapers prior to going to school or taking up light summer jobs that do not interfere with their school timings. When children are given pocket money earning oriented tasks, they understand the value of money, as well as respect it even more.

Child labor coupled with child abuse has today become one of the greatest maladies that have spread across the world. Each year statistics show increasing numbers of child abuse, more so in the case of the girl child. When a girl is probably abused by someone at home, to hide this fact she is sold to an employer from a city as domestic help, or then as a bride to an old man.

Though eradicating the menace seems like a difficult and nearly impossible task, immense efforts have to be made in this direction. The first step would be to become aware of the causes of child labor. The leading reason is that children are employed because they are easier to

exploit. On the other hand, people sell their children as commodities to exploitive employers to have additional sources of income.

Most such employers pay a lump sum for the child and then keep him or her imprisoned within the factory unit till the child cannot work due to deteriorating health as a result of harsh living and working conditions. Lack of proper educational facilities is another reason that forces parents to send their children to work.

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According to the United Nations stipulation in article 32 of the Convention on the Rights of the Child and the International Labor Organization, child labor is to be considered if "States Parties recognize the right of the child to be protected from economic exploitation and from performing any work that is likely to be hazardous or to interfere with the child's education, or to be harmful to the child's health or physical, mental, spiritual, moral or social development."

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India accounts for the second highest number of child labor after Africa. Bonded child labor or slave labor is one of the worst types of labor for children. This system still continues in spite of the Indian Parliament enacting the Bonded Labor System (Abolition) Act in 1976. It is estimated that approximately 10 million bonded children laborers are working as domestic servants in India. Beyond this there are almost 55 million bonded child laborers hired across various other industries.

A recent ILO report says that about 80 per cent of child laborers in India are employed in the agriculture sector. Generally, the children are sold to the rich moneylenders to whom borrowed money cannot be returned. 'Street children' is another type of child labor where children work on the streets as beggars, flower sellers, etc, instead of going to school. Sometimes they are made to go hungry for days together so that people feel sorry for them and give alms.

Among the industries, glass and bangle industry is estimated to employ around 60,000 children who are made to work under extreme conditions of excessive heat. An equal number are estimated to be employed in matchbox factories, where they are made to work over twelve hours a day, beginning work at around 4 a.m., everyday. The brass and the lock industries also employ an estimated 50,000 children each. However, it is the carpet industry in India which employs the largest number of children estimated to be more than four lakhs.

The statistical information regarding child labor cannot be taken to be precise, as there are areas where no accounting has been done. There are innumerable workshops and factories that have cramped up rooms where children work, eat and sleep. No one from the outside world would even know that they are working there. However, people working towards the welfare of child laborers, with the tip-off from insiders, have been able to rescue a number of children from such units.

The National Policy on Child Labor formulated in 1987 seeks to adopt a gradual and sequential approach with a focus on rehabilitation of children working in hazardous occupations and processes. The Action Plan outlined the Legislative Action Plan for strict enforcement of Child Labor Act and other labor laws to ensure that children are not employed in hazardous employments, and that the working conditions of children working in non-hazardous areas are regulated in accordance with the provisions of the Child Labor Act.

It also entails further identification of additional occupations and processes, which are detrimental to the health and safety of the children. Government has accordingly been taking proactive steps to tackle this problem through general strict enforcement of legislative provisions along with simultaneous rehabilitative measures.

To bring the social malady of child labor under control, the government has opened a special cell to help children in exploitive circumstances. These cells comprise of social inspectors, as well as other administrative personnel, employed specifically to deal with child labor issues. Also, in recent years, the media has helped unravel what is happening in certain industrial units with journalists visiting such places with a hidden camera. The efforts made by sections of the government, social workers, non-government organizations and others to rescue and rehabilitate the children must be applauded.

In addition, each individual should also take responsibility of reporting about anyone employing a child below the age of fourteen years. However, considering the magnitude and extent of the problem, concerted efforts from all sections of the society is needed to make a dent. Measures need to be taken not only to stop this crime against children, but also to slowly, steadily and surely provide every child a well-deserved healthy and normal childhood.

A good number of children in Kashmir are directly or indirectly involved in one or other form of child labour and there are approximately 2.50 lakh child workers in the age group of 6-16 years working in various fields of handicrafts sector only. About 47 percent of the total numbers of children work outside their homes regularly for earning and supporting their families. A dominant number of these work in different fields of the handicrafts sector in Jammu and Kashmir. Child labours working in handicrafts sector have come under the focus of academicians, planners, experts and administrators. Several programmes and schemes have been initiated by the governmental and non-governmental organizations for their overall welfare. But the researcher has expressed deep concern over the plight of children who are being used as domestic help.

A significant number of children in the age groups of 6-11 and 11-above, mainly from rural areas, work in the house of businessmen, bureaucrats, politicians, technicians, neo-rich groups and middle class families in the cities and towns. The service conditions of these children are pathetic. In comparison to child labours in other sectors, children in this sector have remained ignored on the part of planners and experts. The plight of these unfortunate children continues without any notice by the society. There were no standards of wages for these child labours at the official or unofficial level. Their wages are determined solely by the heads of the households according to their wishes and preferences.

Fundamental rights of these children are robbed by the individuals and groups which claim to be their protectors. Though some programmes and schemes regarding the eradication of child labour in the state were initiated in the recent past by the government, its impact has not been felt by the suffering children and their families. No fundamental change has occurred in the concerned economic sectors and sections of the society.

1.2. Jammu Kashmir

The state of Jammu and Kashmir is located in the northwest of India. It is a border state and is surrounded by Pakistan, Afghanistan and China on three sides. Indian states of Punjab and Himachal Pradesh touch its borders in the south. The state of Jammu and Kashmir is divided into three distinct geographical regions a) Jammu Province, b) Kashmir valley, and c) Ladakh Plateau. These three regions differ widely with regards to physical, socio- economic and cultural characteristics.

Jammu And Kashmir State is divided into two administrative divisions Jammu and Kashmir. The state has 22 districts, 148 Blocks, 1969 Panchayats, 13786 Panchayat Constituencies, 87 Assembly Constituencies and 6 Parliamentary Constituencies with total population 10,143,700, Kashmir Division 5476,970 (53.9%), Jammu Division 4,430,191 (43.7%) and Ladakh 236,539 (2.3%). District Srinagar of Kashmir Province has total population of 1,202,447 in which 3,69,634 are children with 0-4 years 78,478 and 5-14 years 291,156 (Census2001). The phenomenon of child labour in Jammu and Kashmir is in no way different from that of the one prevailing in the rest of the country. According to census of 2001 in Jammu and Kashmir State 175630 child labour were found. Over the years, child labour has increased tremendously in Jammu and Kashmir particularly in Kashmir Province due to conflict situation from the past 20 years. The education of children has been disturbed in a large number of cases. While child labour remains a serious issue for concern throughout the country, this issue gains an equally, if not more significant attention in the state of J&K. Especially because this issue has been largely neglected by the government and the larger civil society. This is probably because of the priority that the government and the society place in addressing the conflict issues and others. Children instead of attending school and enjoying their childhood are engaged in earning a livelihood, often in harsh circumstances. In 1981 census, the number of child workers reported in J&K was 109,000 and in 1991 census was not conducted in the J&K, figures on the number of the child labour are not available, in 2001 census, the number of child workers reported in J&K was 175630. The Supreme Court had directed in its judgment in December 1996 that a comprehensive survey be done to identify child workers. A survey done by the state government in May 1997 reported 24,000 child workers in hazardous occupations in the Kashmir Division. As per the report published in the daily local English news paper around 250000 child laborers are present in the state. The main work places for child workers in the capital cities of Srinagar and Jammu and other districts of the state are mechanical workshops, automobile workshops, petrol pumps, domestic helpers, bus conductors, carpet weavers, sales man, agriculture helpers etc. Children go to such jobs to earn money to feed their family, many reports from different agencies working for child rights in state stated that most of such children usually fall ill for long span of time and suffer multi diseases. Other form of Labour which we still found in few parts in remote India i.e. Bonded Labour, does not exist in our state but a kind of it can be seen in many villages where children are engaged in Shawl making, carpet weaving etc.

2. Literature Review

The problem of child labour has assumed menacing magnitude and intensity during the twentieth century and continues even in the present era. This study clearly reveals that the problem of child labour in Kashmiri society has wider ramifications. Taking into consideration the causes and

consequences of the problem, the situation reflects an extremely cruel social situation which engulfs socially, economically and educationally back-ward communities. The problem of child labour as existing in Kashmiri society has given rise to multidimensional problems having adverse implications on one's physical, social, emotional, moral and educational development. It is not only social apathy towards child labour but the government in this regard has also shown lack of interest; thereby the problem has become more complex and dangerous. Moreover, the problem of social control, crime and social conflict emanate from the situation without proper care and response, on the part of government and the society at large.

The research findings carried out by B A Bhat in 2009 reveals that the problem of child labour is rooted deep in Kashmiri society, tremendous growth in population accompanied by poverty, illiteracy and ignorance, lack of quality education, etc. are the major causes responsible for child labour. It adversely affects one's personality in terms of its physical, social, emotional, moral and educational development. The study shows that no one is showing concern towards the problem of child labour. Their insecure childhood makes them more vulnerable to exploitation. They face inhuman attitude on the part of their employers. They work in very much dirty environment. Though there are various laws to abolish child labour but they always remained confined to papers as reflected by the action of the government. The present study indicates that total abolition of child labour is neither possible nor desirable so long as there is wide spread poverty, illiteracy and ignorance and unemployment, etc. Far from solving problem, its total abolition will further aggravate it.

Several studies document the phenomenon of child labour in different parts of India. Shandilya & Khan (2003) used mix methods to look at child labour in Patna, the largest city in Bihar (one of the poorest states in India). Under-fed and under-paid, child labourers were found to work for as long as 14 hours a day with 90% of them working under pressure from their families. This study also revealed that majority of the children (62%) reported multiple health problems.

Another study by Devi & Roy (2008) focused mainly on the prevalence of child labour among school children in the rural and urban areas of Pondicherry. They found that the overall prevalence of child labour among students was 32.5% (42.8% in rural and 24.9% in urban areas). Irrespective of the area, educational level of the mother, crowding in the family, families being in debt, presence of a handicapped or alcoholic member in the family, gender and religion were significantly associated with the working child.

Many studies report that poverty is the main reason for child labour (Harper & Karen, 2003; Oyaide, 2000). Sarkar (2007) reported that extreme poverty led to the entry of children into the labour market and their exploitation became common. The author suggests that the employment of child workers in urban India is growing much faster than in rural India and that the four sectors that need to be targeted for the elimination of child labour are manufacturing, transport, storage and communication while wage-based agriculture in rural and urban India must not be ignored. Concurring with Sarkar (2007), Molankal (2008) reported that the core reason for child labour is poverty. Poverty coupled with rapidly growing population, ignorance and increasing dependency load are behind the grim incidence of children employment in the villages and towns of developing countries. The author adds that in India, child labour is not a new phenomenon. It has been in existence since time immemorial in one form or the other and has been changing

from time to time. In the context of Jammu and Kashmir, Shah (1992, pp. 97-101) looked at the informal sector using a mixture of quantitative and qualitative approaches. As is the case in rest of India, the author found children working for long hours ranging from 9-20 hours a day depending on the industry in which they worked. In addition the children were found to be typically under-paid.

In contrast to these studies however, Boyden, Ling, & Myers (1998) suggest that it is too simplistic to attribute child labour to poverty alone. Other factors that have been found to generate child labour include the inadequacy of the school system, geographical location of the family (Kelly, 1998); large family size (Kamocha, Munalula, & Miti, 1997) and family dysfunction due to HIV/AIDS or divorce (Lungwangwa & Macwan'gi, 2004).

There are numerous studies on working children from around the world. However a review of these studies reveals that the children tend to work prolonged and irregular hours, without rest, play, or recreation, suffer from abuse and often live in hazardous conditions (Oyaide, 2000a).

Studies indicate that the burden of household duties fall largely upon the female child. There are jobs that may jeopardise a child's psychological and social growth more than physical growth. In rural areas girls are responsible for looking after younger siblings, cooking, cleaning, fetching, and carrying, which releases adults for productive work. Though a domestic job can involve relatively 'light' work. However, long hours of work, and the physical, psychological and sexual abuse to which the child domestic labourers are exposed make the work hazardous. Studies show that several domestic servants in India on average work for twenty hours a day with small intervals (Nazir Ahmad Shah).

These children are engaged in the unorganised sector where the legislative measures are not implemented. Because of the wide coverage and informal nature of the unorganised sector, monitoring the same becomes an obstacle. Varandani estimated that there were nearly 55 million children in India working as bonded labourers in agriculture, mining, brick-kilns, construction work, fishing activities, carpet weaving, fireworks, matches, glass moulding, bidi-making (cigarettes), gem-cutting and polishing work, electroplating, dyeing, washing and domestic work. About 20 percent of these bonded child labourers were sold to cover some small debts obtained by their parents, usually for some social celebration like a wedding in the family. (Varandani, G. p .42.)

The study of Varanasi carpet industry corroborates it. The manufacturers, weavers and other involved in the industry said that children had nimble fingers and keen eyesight which are essential for accuracy. They will sit in same posture for hours at a time and, all they have very little bargaining power. (Kanbargi, 1988).

According to a study conducted among the street children in the city of Chennai (Madras), about 90% of them live with their parents in the streets. The same study also revealed that the largest group of street children in Chennai work as coolies (22%). About 10.4% of them work in hotels (small restaurants and snack bars), 9.6% do rag picking, 8% pull rickshaws, and 7.1% sell flowers. A smaller percentage of children are employed in other areas of work, including prostitution (0.3%). They work for 10-12 hours a day and at the end of the day what they earn is

barely enough for their survival. About 32% of them receive less than 100 rupees (about 2.5 U.S. Dollars) per month as wages (Joe Arimpoor, 1992).

K Devi, Gautam Roy in his “Study of child labor among school children in Urban and Rural areas of Pondicherry (India)” focused mainly on health. The objective of his study were to determine the prevalence of child labor among school children in the rural and urban areas of Pondicherry; and 2) To study the factors related to child labor - like the reasons for working, problems faced by the child, workplace conditions, etc. In this study also, the methodology is data based, which includes the views of 720 students. His result shows that the overall prevalence of child labor in the study was 32.5%. The number of students who worked in the rural and urban area was 131 (42.8%) and 103 (24.9%) respectively. Irrespective of the area, educational level of the mother, crowding in the family, families being in debt, presence of a handicapped or alcoholic member in the family, gender and religion were significantly associated with the working child.

Research carried by Dr. Tapan Kumar Shandilya under the title “Child labour: A case study of Patna (India)”. The methodology he chose is data collection, which is a mixture Of Quantitative and Qualitative approach. As describing the geographical status of Patna which is Patna, the headquarters of the district as well as the capital of the state, is the largest city in Bihar, having a population of million plus (more than 10 lakhs) as per the provisional population figures of 2001 Census. In his research he has collected the information about 184 (male) children, who worked as a labour, mainly in hotels. Studying their background like the nature and the resources they get. He concluded that given the long working hours, which is around 14 hours much more than the standard normative hours of work (8 hours) for adults and the amount that these children receive, an attempt is made to understand their nutritional level, by the number of times they receive food to eat, its preparation status and adequacy. Giving the information on the number of times children eat food in a day, a quarter (26 percent) of them received food only twice, another 55 percent reported eating food three times a day, while only 18 percent had the opportunity of eating food for four times a day. Given the set-up where these children are working, the status of the food consumed in terms of whether it is fresh preparation or the food consumed is stale food has also been collected. Majority (91 percent) of the children did report that they consumed fresh food, 8 percent mentioned that they ate both fresh and stale food, while one percent received only stale food to eat. Dr. Tapan Kumar Shandilya also reveals that these children were also asked the reason for their working. Nine out of ten children reported that it was the poor economic condition of their family that compelled them to work and analysis made by him on health status, reveals that among all only 70 children out 184 (38percent) had not experienced any sickness in the last six months, while the remaining 114 children in fact also reported multiple problems.

3. Child Labour in India

Child labour is the practice of engaging children in economic activity, on part-time or full-time basis. Contrary to the notion that it is better when all members of a family, irrespective of age, work and earn money, child labour actually makes poverty worse. The more children are forced to work, the fewer opportunities are there for adults to earn a living. By driving down adult wages and depriving children of education, child labour results in poverty passing down from

generation to generation. According to the International Labour Organisation (ILO) “Born to parents who themselves were uneducated child workers, many child workers are forced to continue a tradition that leaves them chained to a life of poverty” (ILO, United States Policies to Address Child Labour globally, 2010). That is why child labour is a very complicated development issue, affecting human society all over the world.

Although India has the largest number of child labourers under the age 14 in the world, child labour problem is not unique to India; worldwide, in many countries children are forced to work with disastrous consequences. Children, under age 14 are often forced to work for as many as 18 hours a day. They are subject to malnutrition, impaired vision, deformities from sitting long hours in cramped over crowded work places, they become easy preys to deadly diseases like serious respiratory diseases, T.B., and Cancer. They are often forced to lead solitary lives away from their families, deprived of meaningful education and training opportunities that could prepare them for a better future. Child labour not only leads to a perpetual cycle of poverty for a family, it depresses the economy also. The immense benefits of abolition of child labour cannot be measured in economic terms alone, its enormous long term beneficial impact on the Society as a whole far outweighs the nominal economic hardship that some families would suffer only for a short span of time.

The following are some of the situations in which children are engaged in work:

- Agriculture- Children working long hours and under severe hardships on the fields. They are also exposed to the hazards of working with modern machinery and chemicals.
- Hazardous Industries/ Occupations- Like glass making, mining, construction, carpet weaving, zari making, fireworks and others as listed under the Child Labour Act.
- Small industrial workshops and service establishments.
- On the streets- Rag pickers, porters, vendors etc.
- Domestic work- Largely invisible and silent and hence face higher degree of exploitation and abuse in the home of employees.

The occupation wise distribution of children engaged in hazardous occupations as per Census of India 2001 shown above. The major occupations engaging child labour are Pan, Bidi & Cigarettes (21%), Construction (17%), Domestic workers (15%) and Spinning & weaving (11%). As per census 2001, Uttar Pradesh (15.22%) recorded the highest share of child labour in the country, followed by Andhra Pradesh (10.76%), Rajasthan (9.97%), Bihar (8.82%), Madhya Pradesh (8.41%), and West Bengal (6.77%).

The census data reveals that, the trend on the magnitude of child labour is not uniform across the country. On one hand, there is considerable increase in the absolute number of child labour between 1991 and 2001 in the states of Uttar Pradesh, Rajasthan, Jharkhand, Chattisgarh, Bihar, West Bengal, Haryana, Uttaranchal, Himachal Pradesh, Punjab, Nagaland, Assam, Meghalaya, and Delhi. On the other hand, Maharashtra, Andhra Pradesh, Madhya Pradesh, Tamil Nadu, Karnataka, Orissa, Gujarat and Kerala have shown significant decline in the number of child labour.

It is also to be noted here that there is a general increasing trend in the magnitude of child labour in the north east region of the country. Sikkim had the highest Child Work Participation Rate

(WPR) in the country with 12.04 % child labourers among total children in the age group of 5-14 years, followed by Rajasthan 8.25 % and Himachal Pradesh (8.14%) during 2001. The other states having higher than the national average of 5 percent WPR for children are Andhra Pradesh (7.7%), Chattisgarh (6.96%), Karnataka (6.91%), Madhya Pradesh (6.71%), J&K (6.62%), Arunachal Pradesh (6.06%), Jharkhand and Assam (5.07%).

The Worker Population Ratio (WPR), defined as the number of persons employed per 1000 persons are available in the Reports of Survey on Employment and Unemployment (NSS 2009-10, 2004-05) broughtout by the National Sample Survey Organisation. There is significant decline in the number of child workers per 1000 by principal usual activity category during 2004-2010.

Table 1: Work Participation of children

		Distribution of (per 1000) of persons by principal usual activity category					
NSS	Age (in years)	Rural		Urban		Total	
		Male	Female	Male	Female	Male	Female
2004-05	5-9	2	1	2	1	2	1
	10-14	54	49	44	24	52	43
2009-10	5-9	2	1	0	0	1	1
	10-14	27	21	24	8	26	18

Source: Key indicators of Employment and unemployment in India, NSS July 2009- June 2010 , Employment and unemployment situation in India

The National Family Health Survey -3 also throws light into the percentage of children age 5-14 years, who were engaged in different activities in the seven days preceding the interview, by background characteristics. As per the NFHS -3 (2005-06), nearly one in every eight (11.8%) children aged 5-14 years works either for their own household or for somebody else. Among the children who work for others, 2.2% children are engaged in paid work and 2.9% are engaged in unpaid work. 3.1% children are engaged in household chores for 28 or more hours in a week, and 4.8% are engaged in work in a family business. Since children are involved in multiple activities, the total work participation rate of 12 percent is less than the sum of the percentages of children engaged in each type of work.

The work participation rate as revealed by NFHS 3 is the same for girls (12 percent) as it is for boys (12 percent). The very young children (age 5-7 years), both boys and girls, are mainly doing unpaid work for someone who is not a member of their household. The older boys age 12-14 are mainly engaged in paid work or family work, whereas girls in this age group are involved mainly in household chores or family work. Notably, at all ages, girls are more likely than boys to be doing chores and boys are more likely than girls to be working for someone who is not a member of the household or doing other family work.

Rural children age 5-14 years (12.9%) are more likely to be engaged in work than their urban counterparts (8.6%). The percentage of children engaged in work activities decreases steadily with mother's increasing education, father's increasing education, and increasing wealth quintile. With parents' higher education and greater household wealth, there is a substantial reduction in

the extent of paid work, involvement in household chores, and other family work, but involvement in unpaid work for someone who is not a member of the household remains more or less the same.

The impact of parent’s education, in sending the children for work is very significant as shown below.

Source: NFHS 3 (2005-06)

Figure 1: Percentage of children working and parent's educational background

Poverty is a prominent cause for child labour, and the NFHS 3 results also reveal this. One in every 7 children in the lowest and second lowest wealth index category is working.

Source: NFHS 3 (2005-06)

Figure 2: Percentage of children 5-14 years working and economic background

About 12.1% children from households headed by Hindus are engaged in work, while the corresponding figure for Muslim and Christian are 10.8% and 7.4% respectively. 16.6% children from households headed by a member of a scheduled tribe are engaged in work while the corresponding figure for Scheduled Caste and Other Backward Class 11.6% and 12.2% respectively.

Child labour denies the child of his basic right that is the right to education. ‘No education’ means unskilled jobs and exploitative wages. This leads to the creation of an unskilled adult labour force which causes early physical decay, economic insecurity, low quality of life and ultimately high poverty. Thus child labour creates a vicious circle of poverty, unemployment, underemployment and low wages. Over the years the Government of India has multiplied its efforts to address the needs and rights of exploited children. Still, the issue remains grave and demanding more rigorous measures. In order to eliminate the social evil of child labour there is a

need for more intensive initiatives to tackle poverty and promote education opportunities to all children to help children and families in crisis.

4. Methodology

Research methodology is a master plan specifying methods and procedures for achieving our goal by collecting and analyzing the needed information. It is one of the important components of research work which enables the researcher to conduct his study in a systematic manner giving a step by step direction from problem identification to data collection to data interpretation. Therefore, this chapter will focus on the research work plan.

4.1. Research Objectives

The study looks at the phenomenon of child labour in district Baramulla. For this purpose, the effect of three independent variables on their three respective dependent variables is investigated. The purpose of research objectives is to determine if the independent variables have significant relationship with the dependent variable or not. The three objectives for this study are as under:

Objectives:

- 1) To find out the factors which are responsible for child labour in District Baramulla?
- 2) To identify the sectors where child labour is most prevalent.
- 3) To understand the effects of working condition on child labors' health.

4.2. Universe of Study

The universe of study was district Baramulla at large and the villages within Baramulla like Palhalan, Nihalpora Hanjiwera Zangam, Sherpora, Sopore, Boniyar, Singpora, Pattan, and Kunzer the data was collected from these villages.

4.3. Data Collection Process

The data collection took around two months; the research went to each of the village and identified the child labours, approached them and motivated them to participate in this research.

4.4. Sample

Mixed sampling was used to reach to the respondents. Quantitative approach was used by adopting both probability method and non – probability method. Two sampling techniques were used, snowball from probability and purposive sampling from non – probability. Snowball technique was used for domestic workers below age of 14 years, whereas from children working in other trades purposive technique was used.

4.5. Sample Size

The total of 100 respondents was approached in ten villages and from each village total of 10 respondents was selected for this study.

4.6. Tools of Data Collection

The data was collected using interview schedule. Research approached to the respondents using interview schedule, this tool for data collection was used to ensure that data collect from respondents will provide enough information about the subject.

4.7. Formation of Data Collection Tool

After the intensive literature review, and study on the topic, the researcher consulted many scholars and other people regarding formation of the data collection tool. The question placed in the interview schedule was already testified by various scholars in their studies. Finally with the consultation with supervisor final interview schedule was framed for the final data collection.

4.8. Data Analysis

The raw data collected from the respondents was scrutinized, tabulated, coded and then frequency test was conducted to understand the percentage of responses, besides frequency test, statistics test like mean and standard deviation was also conducted.

5. Data Analysis and Interpretation

Analyzing the age of the respondents it is revealed that most of the respondents were of the age of 14 years as 37.3 percent of respondents mentioned that. 32 percent of respondents were ageing 13 years, 18.7 percent of respondents are of 12 years age, 5.3 percent of respondents are of just 9 years old whereas 4 percent are of 11 years and 2.7 percent are of 10 years of age.

Age				
	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
9	4	5.3	5.3	5.3
10	2	2.7	2.7	8.0
11	3	4.0	4.0	12.0
Valid 12	14	18.7	18.7	30.7
13	24	32.0	32.0	62.7
14	28	37.3	37.3	100.0
Total	75	100.0	100.0	

The gender of the respondents is mentioned as 52 percent of respondents were male and 48 percent of respondents were female.

Sex

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Male	39	52.0	52.0	52.0
	Female	36	48.0	48.0	100.0
	Total	75	100.0	100.0	

Analysing the child’s monthly earning it is revealed that 93.3 percent of respondents earn INR 500 – 1500 whereas 6.7 percent of respondents earn INR between 1500 – 2500.

Child's Monthly Earning

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	500-1500	70	93.3	93.3	93.3
	1500-2500	5	6.7	6.7	100.0
	Total	75	100.0	100.0	

Finding out the child’s occupation it is revealed through collected data the 30.7 percent of respondents work in Dabha’s (Tea Stalls), 28 percent of them are embroidery workers, 24 percent of the respondents work in automobile sector and 17.3 percent of respondents work as domestic workers.

Child's Occupation

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Automobile	18	24.0	24.0	24.0
	Embroidery				
	Worker	21	28.0	28.0	52.0
	Dabha Work	23	30.7	30.7	82.7
	Domestic Work	13	17.3	17.3	100.0
	Total	75	100.0	100.0	

Understanding the facts about the father's occupation of child labourers it was revealed from the data collected that: 32 percent of respondent's fathers are daily wagers, 29.3 percent of respondent's fathers are doing other works, and 20 percent of respondent's fathers are not alive. 10.7 percent of respondent's fathers are working as drivers and 8 percent of respondent's fathers are working as carpet weavers.

Father's Occupation

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
	Not applicable	15	20.0	20.0	20.0
	Daily wager	24	32.0	32.0	52.0
	Driver	8	10.7	10.7	62.7
Valid	Carpet weaver	6	8.0	8.0	70.7
	Others	22	29.3	29.3	100.0
	Total	75	100.0	100.0	

Analyzing the variable about Mother's occupation of respondent it was revealed that: 92 percent of the respondent's mothers are housewives, 4 percent of respondent's mothers do some work not specified, 2.7 percent of respondent's mothers do farming and 1.3 percent of respondent's mothers are working as tailors.

Mother's Occupation

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Housewife	69	92.0	92.0	92.0
	Farmer	2	2.7	2.7	94.7
	Tailor	1	1.3	1.3	96.0
	Others	3	4.0	4.0	100.0
	Total	75	100.0	100.0	

While analyzing the response of respondents regarding the question are there parents literate. 96 percent of respondents mentioned that their parents are illiterate however 4 percent of respondents revealed that their parents are literate.

Are your parents literate

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Yes	3	4.0	4.0	4.0
Valid No	72	96.0	96.0	100.0
Total	75	100.0	100.0	

In response to question about family monthly income, 65.3 percent of respondents revealed that their family income is in between INR 2000 – 4000 whereas 18.7 percent of respondents mentioned their family income is in between INR 4100 – 6000. 14.7 percent of respondents mentioned that their family income is in between INR 6100 – 8000 and only 1.3 percent of respondents revealed that their family income is above INR 8000 a month.

Family Income monthly

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid 2000-4000	49	65.3	65.3	65.3
Valid 4100-6000	14	18.7	18.7	84.0
Valid 6100-8000	11	14.7	14.7	98.7
Valid Above 8000	1	1.3	1.3	100.0
Total	75	100.0	100.0	

The description of respondent’s family after analyzing the data revealed that 96 percent of respondent belong to nuclear families and just 4 percent of the respondents live in Joint families.

Family Type

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Nuclear Family	72	96.0	96.0	96.0
Valid Joint Family	3	4.0	4.0	100.0
Total	75	100.0	100.0	

Analyzing the data regarding the question “at what age did respondents start to work” 20 percent of respondents mentions that they start working at the age of 11 years, 18.7 percent of respondents mentioned that they start working at the age of 7 years, 16 percent of respondents mentioned that they start work at the age of 8 and 10 years. 12 percent of respondents revealed that they start working at the age of 12 years, 9.3 percent of respondents revealed that they start work at the age of 9 years however, 1.3 and 6.7 percent of the respondents respectively revealed that they start working at the age of 5 and 6 years.

At what age did you start to work for the first time in your life?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
5	1	1.3	1.3	1.3
6	5	6.7	6.7	8.0
7	14	18.7	18.7	26.7

	8	12	16.0	16.0	42.7
Valid	9	7	9.3	9.3	52.0
	10	12	16.0	16.0	68.0
	11	15	20.0	20.0	88.0
	12	9	12.0	12.0	100.0
Total		75	100.0	100.0	

Responding to the question regarding attending the school, 58.6 percent of respondents mentioned that they have attended the school in their life time however, 41.4 percent of respondents revealed that they have never attended the school.

Have you ever attended the school?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Yes	44	58.6	58.6	58.6
No	31	41.4	41.4	100.0
Total	75	100.0		

Analyzing the reasoning for not attending the school it was revealed that; 62.7 percent of respondents mentioned that they cannot afford schooling, 24 percent of respondents mentioned that they were not interested in schooling, 9.3 percent of respondents revealed that their families did not allowed schooling whereas, 4 percent of respondents mentioned they left schooling to work for money.

What was the main reason for not attending the school or why you left the school?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Cannot afford schooling	47	62.7	62.7	62.7
Valid Not interested in schooling	18	24.0	24.0	86.7
Family does not allow schooling	7	9.3	9.3	96.0
To work for money	3	4.0	4.0	100.0
Total	75	100.0	100.0	

Analyzing the response regarding question how they feel working at younger age; 68 percent of the respondents mentioned working at younger age is not good, 22.7 percent of respondents revealed it is good to work at younger age however, 9.3 percent of respondents mentioned that they can't say anything in this regards.

Do you feel that working at younger age is good?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Yes	17	22.7	22.7	22.7
No	51	68.0	68.0	90.7
Can't say	7	9.3	9.3	100.0
Total	75	100.0	100.0	

The data regarding working hours a day revealed that; 45.3 percent of respondents mentioned they work for 9 hours a day, 32 percent of respondents revealed that they work for 10 hours a day. However, 8 percent of respondents mentioned that they work for 11 hours a day and 5.3 percent of respondents revealed that they work 13 hours a day.

How many hours a day you work?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
8	4	5.3	5.3	5.3
9	34	45.3	45.3	50.7
10	24	32.0	32.0	82.7
11	6	8.0	8.0	90.7
12	2	2.7	2.7	93.3
13	4	5.3	5.3	98.7
16	1	1.3	1.3	100.0
Total	75	100.0	100.0	

Analyzing the data regarding working days a week; 49.3 percent of respondents revealed that they work 7 days a week, 48 percent of respondents mentioned that they work 6 days a week; however 2.7 percent of respondents revealed that they work 5 days a week.

How many days you work in a week?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
5	2	2.7	2.7	2.7
6	36	48.0	48.0	50.7
7	37	49.3	49.3	100.0
Total	75	100.0	100.0	

Analyzing the question and employer abuse behaviour; 54.7 percent of respondents mentioned that sometimes their employers abuse them, 37.3 percent of respondents mentioned that their employers doesn't abuse them. However, 8 percent of the respondents revealed that their employers use to abuse them on regular bases.

Does your employer abuse you?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Yes	6	8.0	8.0	8.0
No	28	37.3	37.3	45.3
Sometimes	41	54.7	54.7	100.0
Total	75	100.0	100.0	

In response to question about income and family, 54.7 percent of respondents mentioned that without their income their family cannot manage their household. 42.7 percent of respondents revealed that their income does not affect to their family management. However, 2.7 percent of respondents revealed that they can't say anything about this issue.

Is it so, that without your income your family cannot manage house hold?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Yes	41	54.7	54.7	54.7
No	32	42.7	42.7	97.3
Can't say	2	2.7	2.7	100.0
Total	75	100.0	100.0	

Regarding work and skills development, 48 percent of respondents revealed that they have not been send to only grab skills but to earn too, however 32 percent of respondents mentioned they have been send by their family to grab skills and 20 percent of respondents were not sure about it.

Is it so, that you have been sent to work only to grab skills?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Yes	24	32.0	32.0	32.0
No	36	48.0	48.0	80.0
Not sure	15	20.0	20.0	100.0
Total	75	100.0	100.0	

Analyzing the data regarding the question posed to the respondents about sending their siblings to work at younger age: 69.3 percent of respondents mentioned that they do not want to send their sibling to work at younger age, 17.3 percent of respondents however said they want to send

their siblings to work at younger age. 13.3 percent of respondents were not able to decide hence responded with answer can't say.

Based on your experience will you like to send your sibling to work at younger age?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Yes	13	17.3	17.3	17.3
No	52	69.3	69.3	86.6
Valid Can't say	10	13.3	13.3	100.0
Total	75	100.0		

Analyzing the responses of respondents regarding the question how many times a day they eat food; 98.7 percent of respondents revealed that they take food twice a day, whereas 1.3 percent of the respondents mentioned that they take food thrice a day.

How many times a day you eat food?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Two times	74	98.7	98.7	98.7
Valid Three times	1	1.3	1.3	100.0
Total	75	100.0	100.0	

In response to a question, 50.7 percent of respondents revealed that they was their hands with soap before eating the food, 40 percent of the respondents mentioned that they wash their hands only with water whereas, 1.3 percent of respondents revealed that they do not wash their hands before eating the food.

Before eating food how do you wash your hands?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
With water	36	48.0	48.0	48.0
Without washing	1	1.3	1.3	49.3
Valid With soap	38	50.7	50.7	100.0
Total	75	100.0	100.0	

Responding to question about medical checkup; 100 percent of respondents revealed that they visit doctor whenever they get ill.

After how much time you go for medical checkup?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Whenever get ill	75	100.0	100.0	100.0

In response to a question, is anyone from their family suffering from serious illness; 70.7 percent of respondents mentioned that no one from their family is suffering from any serious illness; however 29.3 percent of respondents mentioned yes any of the family members in their family is suffering from serious illness.

Is anyone from your family suffering from serious illness?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Yes	22	29.3	29.3	29.3
Valid No	53	70.7	70.7	100.0
Total	75	100.0	100.0	

Analyzing the data about a question posed to respondents that how often they fall ill; 86.7 percent of the respondents mentioned that they fall ill sometimes, 10.7 percent of respondents mentioned that they fall ill every month and 2.7 percent of respondents mentioned that they often fall ill.

How often do you fall ill?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Sometimes	65	86.7	86.7	86.7
Valid Every month	8	10.7	10.7	97.3
Valid Often	2	2.7	2.7	100.0
Total	75	100.0	100.0	

The respondents have revealed that 82.7 percent of them have suffered recently from any of the diseases whereas 17.3 percent of them denied suffering from any disease recently.

Do you suffer from any disease recently?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Yes	62	82.7	82.7	82.7
Valid No	13	17.3	17.3	100.0
Total	75	100.0	100.0	

Analyzing the nature of disease; 41.3 percent of respondents revealed that they suffer from Headache / eye problem, 29.3 percent of respondents revealed that they suffer from cold and cough. 14.7 percent of respondents mentioned that suffer from stomach ache and same percentage mentioned that they suffer from skin problem.

What usually is nature of disease?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Cold & cough	22	29.3	29.3	29.3
Stomach ache	11	14.7	14.7	44.0
Valid Skin problem	11	14.7	14.7	58.7
Headache/eye problem	31	41.3	41.3	100.0
Total	75	100.0	100.0	

Analyzing the question that how often they change their clothes; 69.3 percent of respondents revealed that they change their clothes after a week's time. 21.3 percent of respondents mentioned that they change daily however, 9.3 percent of them revealed that they change their clothes after fortnight.

How often you change your clothes?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Every day	16	21.3	21.3	21.3
Weekly	52	69.3	69.3	90.7
Fortnightly	7	9.3	9.3	100.0
Total	75	100.0	100.0	

6. Statistics Graphs

Statistics

	Mother's Occupation	Are your parents literate	Family Income monthly	Family Type	At what age did you start to work for the first time in your life?
Valid N	75	75	75	75	75
Missing	0	0	0	0	0
Mean	1.17	1.96	1.52	1.04	9.13

Statistics

	Have you ever attended the school?	What was the main reason for not attending the school or why you left the school?	Do you feel that working at younger age is good?	How many hours a day you work?	How many days you work in a week?

N	Valid	75	75	75	75	75
	Missing	0	0	0	0	0
Mean		1.40	1.55	1.87	9.81	6.47

Statistics

	Age	Sex	Child's Monthly Earning	Child's Occupation	Father's Occupation
N	Valid	75	75	75	75
	Missing	0	0	0	0
Mean		12.81	1.07	2.41	2.95

Statistics

	Does your employer abuse you?	Is it so, that without your income your family cannot manage house hold?	Is it so, that you have been sent to work only to grab skills?	Based on your experience will you like to send your sibling to work at younger age?	How many times a day you eat food?
N	Valid	75	75	74	75
	Missing	0	0	1	0
Mean		2.47	1.48	1.96	2.01

Statistics

	Before eating food how do you wash your hands?	After how much time you go for medical checkup?	Is anyone from your family suffering from serious illness?	How often do you fall ill?	Do you suffer from any disease recently?
N	Valid	75	75	75	75
	Missing	0	0	0	0
Mean		2.03	4.00	1.71	1.16

Statistics

	What usually is nature of disease?	How often you change your clothes?
N	Valid	75
	Missing	0
Mean		2.68

7. Conclusion and Recommendations

Conclusion

The problem of child labour has assumed menacing magnitude and intensity during the 10th century and continues even in the present era. The present study clearly revealed that the

problem of child labour existing in our society particularly in Baramulla district of Kashmir valley. Taking into consideration the causes and consequences of the problem, the situation reflects an extremely cruel social situation which engulfs socially economically and educationally backward communities. Child labour from ancient times existed in all the countries of the world with varying degrees and magnitude. Children continue to constitute an important source of cheap labour supply. They were either required to help their parents in domestic work grazing cattle and farming, or earning from their parents in labour market where they work in houses or workshops of their masters. The advent of high technology and economic development brought no change in the employment of child labour which prevails even now, both in developed and developing countries of the world. The unorganized sector in the Jammu and Kashmir state is more dominant and it ranks high, in respect of employment of children in the whole country. The study makes a detailed analysis of the problems faced by children in the unorganized sector in Baramulla district of Kashmir valley.

The problem of child labour as it exists in the society has given rise to multidimensional problems having adverse implications on the physical, social, and educational development of the affected children. Because of the policies made by the Government of India as implemented through the National Child Labour Project, the child labourers working in the Handicraft sector get a chance to obtain informal education. However, more efforts on part of the government are required as most of the child labourers are not able to benefit from projects because of their long working hours, and because of their parents' ignorance about the utility of education. On the other hand, children working in the automobile sector do not get any such chance of obtaining education. Efforts also need to be made to address this. This study upholds the view that child labour exists with high intensity and complexity in the informal sector.

Effects of Child Labour

Some conscientious employers, child welfare activists, medical practitioners, social workers, adult labours and labour leaders vehemently criticized the practice of child labour employment as it leads to economic exploitation and psycho - physical breakdown of child labour. The reasons advanced by them in support of their contention unveil the adverse effects of child labour.

Exploitation of child labour: The employers guided by the doctrine of self interest exploit the low bargaining power of children through paying them lower wages and making them work for longer hours as revealed by this study.

Promotion of illiteracy: The lure of earning subsistence wages keeps a good number of children away from the portals of learning and reading. Barring a microscopic minority who combine education with work, child labour, in general, promotes illiteracy in the society. The same has been upheld by the finding of this study.

Health Hazards: The most worst effect of child labour is that it leads to physiological and psychological deformities of the child.

The longer hours of work, bad and unhygienic working conditions and sitting in wrong postures lead to retarded growth, orthopedic diseases, respiratory problems etc. which the study showed in

the findings. The working children feel insecure and suffer from an inferiority complex. As such, their physical and mental growth suffers and thus nation on the whole loses a vast potential of human resource.

Suggestions and Recommendations

The state government, social agencies, non – governmental agencies, civil societies and other voluntary organizations have a big role to play to save the children falling an easy prey to the mechanizations of the greedy and crafty employers. Since the magnitude of the problem is too big and complex to handle by the state alone hence all the players have to play role fighting this social issue.

At Civil Society Level

- Civil society should get organized and try to address the issues of child labour through social movements.
- Support should be given to those families who have child labour by motivating them to organize and encourage for proper skills development and education.

At Government Level

- Government should take bold steps to enforce the laws to abolish child labour.
- Government should ensure financial support to down trodden families in order to provide education and health facilities to their children.
- Government should take up steps and consult scholars, academicians, planners belonging to different streams in order to frame policies about the future and overall development of these children work as child labours.

Policy Implications

Before concluding this paper, it serves well to highlight the policy implications of this paper. Based on review of literature and field experiences, we conclude that child labour cannot be straight away banned in developing countries; it can however be controlled. This is primarily due to the embeddedness of child labor in the socio-economic structures and set up of the society. Basu & Van (1998), Dessy (2000) and Soares (2010) too realized this and suggested that banning child labour alone is not likely to be effective in practice. A ban on child labour would be difficult to enforce, especially in the rural areas of the country (Brown, 2001). In India, a good 5% of the economy is supported by child labour (Basu, 1999). Therefore a ban on this practice, besides being difficult to enforce, will not even serve the purpose of ensuring improvement in children's welfare as 54% of the child labourers studied in this paper indicated child labourers' income as indispensable to their family. In case of not being able to meet their sustenance needs minus income from child labourers, all such families may face greater problems and even force children into more hazardous jobs (Bachman, 2000). The concerned authorities can, nevertheless, create awareness among masses in general and among illiterate people in particular about the nature of crime committed by employing a child either as domestic help or otherwise. The concerned authorities can improve condition of the child labourers by introducing attractive

and free pre-primary and primary school education system to woo the children. Imparting skill-based education at the school level can reduce worries of unemployment among parents and discourage child labour. As is the case in many countries, the government can decrease minimum age limit for skill-based workers. The concerned authorities can also regulate children working as child labourers for 4-5 years and ensure that the employers pay them fixed wages provide them with benefits like medical facilities, provident fund facilities, and other benefits enjoyed by regular adult workers. Community based school extension programmes, brought in as a result of effective policy-making, can raise awareness about benefits and necessity of education and encourage children to go to schools.

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